

GRAPH-BASED TRAVEL-TIME MODELING FOR HOSPITAL TRANSPORT SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT. Accurate travel time modeling is essential for credible discrete-event simulation of internal hospital logistics, as it directly influences workload estimation, resource utilization, and system dynamics. However, most simulation studies rely on static distance-based heuristics or aggregated statistics that fail to capture the stochastic and context-dependent nature of real hospital operations. In practice, travel times are highly variable, sparsely observed, and often missing for many origin–destination relations, particularly for empty porter movements. This paper presents a data-driven framework that reconstructs a latent operational topology from historical transport logs using graph embeddings and combines it with context-aware quantile regression to estimate travel time distributions for both loaded and empty movements. By learning operational proximity rather than geometric distance, the framework enables imputation for sparsely observed and previously unseen routes. The method is evaluated on operational data from three German hospitals using a two-layer validation strategy. Predictive experiments show improved accuracy and uncertainty calibration for unseen routes compared with common simulation input baselines. When integrated into a trace-driven discrete-event simulation, the learned travel-time distributions produce system-level behavior that more closely matches historically observed workload and utilization patterns without modifying dispatching logic or system capacity. The results demonstrate a practical approach for constructing complete, uncertainty-aware travel time inputs for hospital logistics simulation under sparse operational data.

Keywords: Simulation input modeling, discrete-event simulation, travel-time uncertainty, graph embedding

1. INTRODUCTION

Internal Hospital Logistics (IHL) concerns the coordination of patient transports and the movement of medical equipment and supplies within hospital facilities [11]. Unlike many manufacturing logistics, which often operate under relatively controlled schedules, IHL is a highly dynamic and human-centered system characterized by substantial stochasticity [10]. Transport execution is affected by frequent interruptions, fluctuating demand, and unpredictable delays arising from elevator contention, corridor congestion, and emergency prioritization [2].

In this context, discrete-event simulation (DES) has become a standard methodology for analyzing hospital logistics systems and supporting decisions related to porter fleet sizing, dispatching logic, and scheduling policies [8]. The credibility of such simulation studies, however, depends critically on the realism of their input models [1]. As emphasized by Law [13], even highly sophisticated control logic cannot compensate for an inaccurate system representation.

One of the most influential yet frequently oversimplified input components in hospital simulation is *internal travel time*. A typical transport task consists of two distinct phases: an *empty travel* (dead-heading) phase, during which a porter moves to a pickup location, and a *loaded transport* phase, during which a patient or material is conveyed to its destination. Despite their impact on cycle times and workload, these durations are often modeled using static assumptions such as constant speeds, global

averages, or shortest-path heuristics derived from physical layouts [11]. Such deterministic abstractions fail to capture operational reality, as they neglect the friction induced by vertical transport (e.g., elevator waiting times), mode-specific constraints (e.g., bed versus walking transport), and the strongly context-dependent nature of hospital traffic [4].

In practice, historical transport logs collected from real hospitals are a primary data source for modeling internal travel times. A common approach is to construct statistical baseline models from these logs, for example by assigning the median observed travel time to each origin–destination (OD) pair. For routes that are executed frequently under routine operating conditions, such estimators can reasonably reflect past system behavior and are therefore often used as baseline inputs in simulation studies. However, this approach has two fundamental limitations.

Hospital transport data is inherently sparse, not due to data quality issues but as a natural consequence of routine hospital operations. While a limited set of high-traffic routes is executed repeatedly, many valid OD relations are observed only infrequently or not at all. This sparsity becomes particularly problematic when hospitals undergo operational changes, such as ward relocations or temporary infrastructure restrictions, for which historical data provides little guidance.

The focus of this paper is not route optimization or geometric distance estimation, but the construction of realistic, complete, and uncertainty-aware travel time input models. Addressing this challenge under conditions of data sparsity and operational dynamics requires modeling approaches that extend beyond static heuristics. Accordingly, we represent the hospital as an operational network reconstructed directly from historical transport logs rather than from physical layouts.

We propose a data-driven framework for modeling internal hospital travel times under uncertainty. The framework utilizes graph embeddings to reconstruct a latent operational topology from sparse execution logs and combines this representation with context-aware quantile regression to estimate travel time distributions for both empty and loaded transport. In contrast to static baseline methods, the proposed approach supports generalization to previously unobserved routes and explicitly represents uncertainty. We evaluate the method using real operational data from three German hospitals. The results demonstrate improved generalization on unseen routes compared to common baseline models. Furthermore, a trace-driven discrete-event simulation confirms that replacing static travel time assumptions with the proposed uncertainty-aware inputs leads to system-level behavior that is operationally plausible and consistent with observed ranges, particularly regarding porter utilization and workload dynamics.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on simulation-based hospital logistics and travel time modeling. Section 3 introduces the operational context and data structure. Section 4 presents the proposed methodology. Section 5 describes the experimental design, while Section 6 reports the results. Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. RELATED WORK

This work connects discrete-event simulation (DES) for internal hospital logistics with data-driven operational modeling and graph representation learning. The related literature is organized into three strands: simulation-based hospital logistics, operational travel time modeling under uncertainty, and graph-based learning approaches in transportation systems.

2.1. Simulation in Hospital Logistics. Discrete-event simulation is widely used to study internal hospital logistics, primarily for evaluating dispatching strategies, and request scheduling. In most existing models, travel times are treated as deterministic parameters derived from physical distance or static lookup tables, while uncertainty is considered mainly at the level of transport request arrivals. This modeling practice remains prevalent in recent studies published between 2022 and 2024 [17, 15, 3],

where simulation is employed to analyze control policies under fixed travel time assumptions. Consequently, the realism of simulation outcomes is fundamentally limited by the fidelity of the underlying system representation, regardless of the sophistication of the applied control logic.

2.2. Operational Travel Time Modeling. Klein and Thielen [11] review 22 core studies on intra-hospital patient transport and report that, although uncertainty is frequently acknowledged, only a small subset of studies (4 out of 22) explicitly consider travel time uncertainty. In these cases, uncertainty is typically handled reactively, for example through re-optimization after disruptions, rather than being incorporated as a predictive input at the planning stage.

Explicit predictive modeling of travel time uncertainty in hospital transport systems therefore remains comparatively rare. Examples include Hanne et al. [9], who study robustness and online decision-making in patient transport operations, and van den Berg and van Essen [16], who address maintaining service coverage under uncertain response times. These approaches primarily address uncertainty through robustness concepts or buffers, rather than through explicit estimation of route-specific travel time distributions.

More recently, Kropp et al. [12] analyze patient transport processes using data-driven methods within a process-mining framework. While effective for analyzing observed processes, such approaches may have limited ability to generalize to unobserved Origin–Destination (OD) pairs. Other recent ensemble-based approaches [18] similarly rely on supervised learning and engineered features, but may continue to face challenges related to data sparsity and generalization across the operational transport network.

2.3. Graph Representation Learning in Transportation. While underexplored in indoor healthcare, graph-based learning is the state-of-the-art in broader transportation systems. In ride-hailing and traffic prediction (e.g., Google Maps), simple averaging has been replaced by Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) that learn the traffic connectivity of road segments [5]. In automated and large-scale transportation networks, recent work leverages graph-based representations to learn node and edge embeddings that approximate shortest-path distances and travel times directly from network topology, enabling efficient distance estimation and routing without explicit path enumeration [14].

Our work transfers this paradigm to a hospital. Unlike road-based transportation networks, hospital transport operations involve vertical transport constraints and complex mode-switching (walking vs. bed pushing). By applying Node2Vec [7] to learn the *operational manifold* of the hospital, we provide a method capable of imputing travel times for unobserved routes in simulation, addressing the limitations of standard statistical and tabular ML approaches.

3. OPERATIONAL CONTEXT AND DATA STRUCTURE

In large modern hospitals, internal logistics is a continuous and predominantly human-centered operation that supports clinical workflows around the clock. Transport tasks are initiated by clinical staff whenever patients, beds, materials, or medical supplies need to be moved between functional units such as wards, diagnostic departments, operating theaters, and storage areas. These tasks are executed by porters under varying workload conditions, infrastructure constraints, and organizational rules. As a result, internal travel time is a key factor influencing overall operational performance.

3.1. Transport Process Lifecycle. Internal hospital transport follows a request-to-execution lifecycle in which transport orders are continuously generated, queued in a backlog, and assigned to available porters. After assignment, execution consists of two operationally distinct movement phases, which play different roles in the transport process and therefore require separate treatment in simulation.

Empty movements are typically initiated autonomously by porters and are executed either by walking or by using passenger elevators to reach the pickup location. In contrast, loaded transports depend on the

specific task type and are subject to stricter operational constraints. The majority of loaded transports fall into three categories: patient transfers, material logistics, and medical supplies [6], each associated with different transport modes such as beds, wheelchairs, trolleys, or manual carrying. These modes impose heterogeneous routing and accessibility constraints. For example, bed transport depends on elevator availability and wide corridors, whereas walking allows for more flexible routing, including the use of stairs to bypass congestion.

These systematic differences motivate an explicit separation of empty and loaded travel times in the proposed modeling approach. Waiting times and reaction delays may occur within this lifecycle but are outside the scope of this study.

3.2. Operational Variability and Simulation Scope. Hospital transport operations exhibit strong temporal variability. Workload levels fluctuate over the course of the day and week, with peak activity during regular working hours and reduced demand during nights and non-working days (Figure 1). In addition to these routine fluctuations, hospitals experience non-routine disruptions, such as elevator outages, temporary access restrictions, or short-term infrastructure changes.

FIGURE 1. Transport execution time distributions across hourly intervals, separated by working and non-working days, for three hospitals.

While historical transport logs mainly reflect standard operating conditions, simulation-based studies require input models that remain valid under peak-load and disruption scenarios. This requirement is particularly challenging for sparsely observed OD relations, for which historical data is often limited.

3.3. Data Structure. The empirical basis of this study consists of historical transport logs collected from three German hospitals, hereafter referred to as Hospital A, B, and C. All hospitals use the same transport management system, resulting in an identical data structure across sites. The general characteristics of the three hospitals are summarized in Table 1. Each transport record captures information available at order creation as well as during execution (see Table 2). Importantly, no explicit geometric layout, distance information, or routing data is available. Hence, the simulation input model must be derived entirely from operational log data.

TABLE 1. Overview of general hospital logistics characteristics.

Hospital	Segments	Locations	Avg. Daily Orders	Avg. Daily Porters	% Emergency	Avg. Travel Time (min)
A	5	156	436	19	2.31%	5.31
B	5	111	583	21	11.45%	6.40
C	2	105	244	10	1.44%	9.84

Before introducing learning-based models, we first verify that travel time uncertainty is empirically significant and inherent to the operational logs. By analyzing internal transport data collected over a

TABLE 2. Structure of Transport Orders and Operational Attributes

Category	Attributes and Description
Temporal	Order creation timestamp; planned execution window; actual execution timestamps; weekdays and holidays
Spatial	Origin and destination locations (e.g., wards, diagnostic units); location granularity varies across hospitals
Task Type	Type of transport task (patient, material, supplies)
Transport Mode	Required modality (bed, wheelchair, trolley, walking)
Urgency	Different classes of transport urgency
Execution Duration	Observed duration of empty and loaded transport phases, derived from timestamps

FIGURE 2. travel time variability for the 10 busiest routes (left) and the corresponding feature-importance results (right) for Hospital A.

seven-year period, we observe that execution times for identical OD routes exhibit substantial variability.

As an illustrative example, Figure 2 (left) shows the travel time distributions of the ten busiest routes in Hospital A, which exhibit substantial variability. To analyze the drivers of this variability, we conduct a feature-importance analysis using a high-capacity tabular regression model (Figure 2, right). In addition, we examine whether the contextual attributes listed in Table 2 correspond to systematic differences in observed travel times, rather than serving merely as auxiliary metadata. For this purpose, we conduct a two-part empirical analysis:

- **OD-Controlled Comparisons:** Origin–destination–controlled comparisons assess whether travel times differ systematically across contextual feature values within identical routes. By normalizing observations at the route level, this analysis reduces the influence of spatial heterogeneity and isolates effects related to operational conditions.
- **Predictive Relevance:** Feature importance is evaluated by measuring the increase in prediction error when individual contextual features, such as transport mode, time of day, emergency flag, or working-day indicator, are removed from the regression model.

Together, these analyses demonstrate that contextual features explain meaningful operational variability in internal hospital transport processes. However, conditioning travel time estimates on multiple contextual dimensions inevitably fragments the empirical data. We therefore conclude this section by quantifying the resulting sparsity, reported in Table 3, which motivates the graph-based representation learning approach introduced in Section 4.

TABLE 3. Sparsity of loaded travel time matrices under increasing context dimensionality.

	Hospital A			Hospital B			Hospital C		
	Level	Observed	Possible	Sparsity	Observed	Possible	Sparsity	Observed	Possible
OD only	5,088	23,408	0.78	3,864	11,660	0.67	1,948	10,500	0.81
OD + transport type	9,483	93,632	0.90	4,956	34,980	0.86	2,460	42,000	0.94
OD + transport type + emergency	9,974	187,264	0.95	5,568	69,960	0.92	2,565	84,000	0.97
OD + transport type + emergency + hour	54,802	4,494,336	0.99	22,435	1,679,040	0.99	10,994	2,016,000	0.99
OD + transport type + emergency + hour + working day	68,814	8,988,672	0.99	29,253	3,358,080	0.99	12,867	4,032,000	1.00

Rationale for operational attribute selection. The operational attributes in Table 2 were selected for their relevance to transport execution and their consistent availability across hospitals. While richer information, such as physical layouts, corridor geometry, or real-time staffing and visitor counts, would in principle influence travel times, such data is typically unavailable, incomplete, or highly hospital-specific. In contrast, the selected attributes are reliably recorded in transport logs and reflect dominant operational constraints, including transport modality, urgency, and temporal workload effects. As shown in Figure 2, these attributes explain systematic travel time variability even after controlling for OD relations, enabling a pragmatic abstraction that supports cross-hospital generalization.

3.4. Empirical Challenges and Baseline Estimates. In the hospital transport setting, dispatching and routing decisions depend on OD travel time information across a large set of potential location pairs. This need is particularly pronounced for empty travel, where porters may be dispatched from many possible locations, whereas loaded transports tend to follow more regular patterns. In the three hospitals analyzed in this study, the empirical data are highly incomplete: at least 67% of all feasible OD connections are never directly observed in the historical logs.

To address this challenge, several baseline strategies can be applied in practice. We use the following approaches as reference models for evaluating the proposed framework.

Baseline A: Context-Conditioned Empirical Median. This baseline computes travel time as the median of historical observations. It relies exclusively on data that exactly matches the requested OD pair and operational context. While this approach provides accurate estimates for frequently used routes (“high-traffic edges”), it suffers from substantial coverage gaps due to the strict context matching. In the simulation, missing values must therefore be replaced by global aggregate statistic, which leads to inaccurate estimates for rarely observed routes.

Baseline B: Hierarchical Back-Off Median. To mitigate the sparsity of Baseline A, this approach applies a hierarchical relaxation strategy. If no observations exist for a specific context (e.g., “bed transport at 8:00 AM”), the estimator progressively falls back to more general groups (e.g., “bed transport” → “all transports”). This back-off mechanism improves coverage but may still rely on coarse aggregates and introduces bias by neglecting context-specific operational effects, such as congestion or elevator availability.

Baseline C: Topology-Based Shortest-Path Approximation. This baseline constructs an empirical graph in which edges are weighted by median travel times between directly connected locations. Travel times for unobserved OD pairs are inferred using shortest-path algorithms such as Dijkstra, which allows the method to cope with data sparsity. However, this approach implicitly assumes optimal and additive routing behavior and therefore tends to underestimate actual travel times.

These baselines highlight a fundamental trade-off. Empirical approaches (Baselines A and B) preserve observed behavior but break down for sparsely observed or unobserved routes. In contrast, topology-based heuristics (Baseline C) alleviate sparsity through graph-based inference but introduce an optimistic bias that leads to underestimated travel times. This trade-off motivates the methodology

presented in Section 4, which leverages graph representation learning to reconstruct the operational topology and to generate more realistic travel time estimates, including for sparsely observed routes.

4. METHODOLOGY

This section describes a data-driven pipeline for constructing simulation-ready travel time inputs from historical hospital transport logs. The framework reconstructs the operational topology of the hospital and generates stochastic travel time estimates for all OD pairs. It consists of four stages: (i) operational graph construction, (ii) latent topology learning via graph embeddings, (iii) context-aware uncertainty modeling, and (iv) matrix imputation.

As discussed in Section 1, travel times are stochastic, context-dependent, and sparsely observed. We therefore model operational proximity rather than physical distance and combine it with uncertainty-aware regression to generate simulation-ready travel time distributions.

4.1. Operational Graph Construction. The first stage transforms raw transport logs into a structured representation suitable for learning. This step consists of two parallel processes: extracting explicit loaded travel times and inferring implicit empty movements. Together, these processes provide the training data and define the topology of the operational graph.

Feature Engineering and Matrix Extraction. Two distinct datasets are derived from the transport logs. The *Loaded Travel Time Matrix* is constructed directly from individual transport orders, where travel duration is computed as the difference between pickup and delivery timestamps. While the raw data contains a large number of transport types, these are systematically aggregated into five operationally meaningful categories: (1) lying patient transport, (2) sitting patient transport, (3) material pushing (e.g., carts or trolleys), (4) material carrying (manual transport without devices), and (5) empty walking movements. This abstraction preserves dominant physical and organizational constraints, such as elevator usage for lying patient transport or reduced maneuverability for pushed devices, while substantially mitigating data sparsity.

In contrast, the *Empty Travel Time Matrix* cannot be observed directly, as porter repositioning movements are not explicitly recorded in the logs. These deadheading movements are reconstructed by grouping transport orders by porter and sorting them temporally to form execution tours. For two consecutive orders O_i and O_{i+1} within the same tour, an empty movement is defined from the delivery location of O_i to the pickup location of O_{i+1} . To avoid implausible inferences, several filtering rules are applied, including the exclusion of overlapping assignments, cancelled orders without execution, and long idle intervals that indicate breaks or shift boundaries. This procedure yields a consistent set of inferred empty movements that complements the directly observed loaded travel times.

Graph Topology Definition. Based on the extracted loaded and empty movements, we construct a directed operational graph $G = (V, E)$. Each node $u \in V$ represents a unique operational location, such as a ward, operating theater, or diagnostic unit. A directed edge $e_{uv} \in E$ is created if at least one transport from location u to location v is observed in the training data.

Importantly, edges in G represent *empirical operational connectivity* rather than geometric adjacency. To encode the relative importance of connections, each edge is weighted by its observed transport frequency W_{uv} . This frequency-weighted representation emphasizes frequently used logistical corridors while preserving rare but operationally valid routes.

4.2. Latent Topology Learning via Node Embeddings. Operational graphs derived from historical logs are inherently sparse, as many feasible OD pairs are never observed directly. To generalize beyond observed edges, we apply graph representation learning to infer latent structural relationships between locations.

We employ a Node2Vec embedding approach to map each node $u \in V$ to a low-dimensional vector $z_u \in \mathbb{R}^d$. From a simulation perspective, Node2Vec is particularly suitable because it captures topological similarity rather than relying on geometric distance. Locations that fulfill similar operational roles, such as wards served by the same elevator core or departments with comparable accessibility constraints, are embedded close to each other in the latent space, even if no direct connection exists in the observed graph.

The resulting embedding space can be interpreted as a *latent operational manifold*, where distances reflect effective transport friction induced by organizational structure, vertical transport constraints, and recurring congestion patterns. This representation enables principled extrapolation to unobserved routes based on the learned proximity of their endpoints. Node2Vec is applied using standard random-walk sampling and skip-gram optimization; hyperparameters are fixed across hospitals and reported in Section 5.

4.3. Context-Aware Uncertainty Modeling. Internal hospital travel times are both stochastic and context-dependent. We therefore formulate travel time estimation as a supervised regression problem conditioned on spatial topology and operational context.

For each transport task from origin o to destination d , we construct a feature vector

$$(1) \quad x_{od} = [z_o \oplus z_d \oplus \tau_{\text{hour}} \oplus \rho_{\text{prio}} \oplus \mu_{\text{mode}}],$$

where z_o and z_d are the learned node embeddings, τ_{hour} encodes the time of day, ρ_{prio} denotes task priority, and μ_{mode} represents the transport category. This formulation allows simulation inputs to adapt dynamically to varying operational conditions, such as peak hours or mode-specific constraints.

To explicitly model uncertainty, we employ a gradient boosting regressor trained with a quantile loss function. Rather than producing a single point estimate, the model predicts the 10th, 50th, and 90th percentiles of the travel time distribution. This captures both *aleatoric uncertainty*, arising from congestion and elevator waiting times, and *epistemic uncertainty*, resulting from sparse observations of rare routes.

4.4. Full Matrix Imputation for Simulation. In the final stage, the trained model is used to generate simulation-ready travel time inputs for the complete set of ordered location pairs $(u, v) \in V \times V$. For each pair, travel time distributions are predicted under fixed contextual settings, yielding dense OD matrices that can be queried directly by the simulation.

The imputation is performed separately for each transport category defined in Section 4.1, allowing the simulation to retain mode-specific dynamics while avoiding reliance on sparse empirical observations. Where required by the simulation scope or data availability, these categories can be aggregated without modifying the underlying learning pipeline.

The resulting matrices provide uncertainty-aware lookup tables that support dispatching and routing decisions even for routes that were never directly observed in the historical logs, thereby enabling robust simulation of system-wide operational behavior.

5. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN AND EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

We evaluate the proposed framework using a two-layer experimental design. Layer I assesses predictive accuracy of travel time models on previously unseen OD relations. Layer II evaluates the operational impact of these inputs in a trace-driven discrete-event simulation under fixed and simple control logic. This separation allows us to isolate improvements in travel time estimation from their downstream effects on system behavior.

5.1. Implementation Overview. All experiments are implemented in Python using standard scientific libraries. Operational graphs and node embeddings are constructed using `NetworkX` and `node2vec`, while learning-based models are trained using gradient boosting. The discrete-event simulation is implemented using `SimPy`. Figure 3 summarizes the experimental setup for both evaluation layers.

5.2. Evaluation Layer I: travel time Prediction. Layer I evaluates the accuracy and uncertainty calibration of travel time models on unseen OD routes. A strict route-level train-test split is applied, ensuring that all test routes are unobserved during training. This setting explicitly assesses model generalization under cold-start conditions. To prevent information leakage, the operational graph used for representation learning is constructed exclusively from training-set edges. Random walks for `Node2Vec` are therefore generated only on the training graph G_{train} , which excludes all OD relations reserved for testing. Node embeddings are learned without exposure to test routes.

Graph-Based Model. We evaluate the graph-based travel time prediction model introduced in Section 4, which combines node embeddings with operational context features and predicts travel time quantiles using a gradient boosting regressor.

Tabular Baseline. To isolate the contribution of latent topology learning, we include a strong tabular baseline that uses the same quantile gradient boosting regressor but replaces graph embeddings with one-hot encoded origin and destination identifiers. All remaining features and hyperparameters are kept identical.

Evaluation Metrics. Predictive performance is assessed using Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) on the median prediction. Uncertainty calibration is evaluated via empirical coverage of the predicted $[q_{10}, q_{90}]$ interval and the corresponding mean interval width.

5.3. Layer II: Simulation-Based Evaluation of travel time Inputs. While Layer I evaluates predictive accuracy at the route level, it does not reveal how travel time estimation errors propagate through a discrete-event simulation (DES). Layer II therefore evaluates the proposed model strictly in its intended role: as an *input model* for hospital transport simulation. The objective is not to reproduce historical operations exactly, but to assess whether alternative travel time inputs induce materially different system-level behavior under identical control logic.

Simulation scope and operational dynamics. We implement a trace-driven discrete-event simulation (DES) using `SimPy`, representing a single internal transport department with pooled porters, FIFO dispatching (i.e. requests are assigned strictly in order of arrival), and non-preemptive task execution. Transport *demand arrivals* (order release times, origins, destinations, and transport categories) are replayed from historical logs to isolate the effect of travel time inputs. All remaining operational dynamics, including porter availability, task assignment, travel progression, and queue formation are modeled within the simulation.

Crucially, only travel times are replaced by model outputs. Reaction delays and service times at pickup and delivery locations are sampled directly from their empirical distributions conditioned on transport category, but are not fixed per order. This ensures that waiting times, backlog evolution, and utilization emerge from the interaction between stochastic travel times and the dispatching policy, rather than being implicitly replayed.

travel time input models. For each transport execution within the simulation, the required loaded or empty travel time is sampled from the corresponding OD distribution produced by the evaluated model. For the proposed approach, we draw from the predicted conditional quantile distribution using inverse transform sampling between (q_{10}, q_{90}) . Baseline models provide deterministic or stochastic samples according to their respective definitions. All models are queried at runtime using identical contextual information.

Experimental design. The simulation is executed independently under each travel time input model using: (i) identical demand traces, (ii) identical dispatching logic and resource configurations, and (iii) identical random seeds for non-travel time stochastic components. Each scenario is simulated for three consecutive months (May–July 2019) with a one-week warm-up period. To reduce stochastic variance, all scenarios are replicated ten times and results are reported as averages.

Evaluation metrics. We report system-level key performance indicators commonly used in hospital logistics DES studies: porter utilization, average and peak backlog, task completion count, and the proportion of time spent in loaded travel, empty travel, and waiting states. These metrics are compared across input models and against the historical reference to assess whether improved travel time realism translates into more plausible operational dynamics.

Interpretation. Layer II does not claim to validate the dispatching policy itself. Instead, it isolates the sensitivity of DES outcomes to travel time inputs. A travel time model is considered superior in this context if it yields stable, non-degenerate simulations and system-level indicators that are consistent with observed operational ranges without requiring policy retuning.

FIGURE 3. Experimental setup overview for Layer I (travel time modeling) and Layer II (trace-driven simulation).

Layer I: Graph Embedding		Layer I: Learning Setup		Records After Cleaning			
Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value	Hospital	A	B	C
Method	Node2Vec	Split strategy	Route-level	#Records	599,666	473,120	336,536
Dimensionality	32	Train/test ratio	80/20	Layer II: Simulation Setup			
Walks / node	20	Random seed	42	Parameter	Value		
Walk length	30	Quantiles	0.1, 0.5, 0.9	Framework	SimPy		
Context window	5	Regressor	Quantile GBR	Horizon per run	24h (daily)		
Epochs	10	Trees	250	Simulation period	May–July 2019		
p, q	1.0, 1.0	Max depth	5	Aggregation	Mean KPI over days		
Graph	Directed, weighted	Target	$\log(1 + t)$				

6. RESULTS

This subsection reports the predictive performance of the evaluated travel time models on previously unseen OD relations under the route-level evaluation protocol described in Section 5. The objective of this layer is to assess generalization performance under cold-start conditions, where no historical observations are available for the evaluated routes.

Table 4 summarizes point prediction accuracy and uncertainty calibration across all hospitals. The proposed graph-embedding regressor achieves the lowest MAE and RMSE in all cases. Compared to the tabular machine learning baseline with one-hot encoded origin and destination identifiers, error reductions are consistent across hospitals, indicating that performance gains primarily stem from topology-aware representation learning rather than from the regression model itself.

Heuristic median-based baselines show substantially higher errors, particularly for larger and more heterogeneous hospitals. The shortest-path baseline performs reasonably for smaller datasets but degrades as route sparsity increases, reflecting the limitations of purely graph-theoretic extrapolation without learned latent representations.

Uncertainty estimates produced by the proposed model are well calibrated, with empirical coverage of the predicted $[q_{10}, q_{90}]$ interval close to the nominal 80% level while maintaining compact interval widths. This balance between reliability and sharpness is essential for downstream simulation use, where overly conservative uncertainty can distort system dynamics.

TABLE 4. Layer I — Predictive performance on unseen OD routes (seconds).

Hospital	Model	MAE ↓	RMSE ↓	Coverage q10–q90 ↑	Mean Interval Width ↓
Hospital A	Proposed (Embeddings + Quantile GBR)	49.1	59.1	0.76	193.9
	ML Baseline (One-Hot OD + Quantile GBR)	68.9	74.6	0.72	184.7
	Baseline A (Context Median + Fallback)	106.3	111.2	–	–
	Baseline B (Hierarchical Backoff Median)	69.6	74.6	–	–
	Baseline C (Shortest Path + Fallback)	247.0	265.0	–	–
Hospital B	Proposed (Embeddings + Quantile GBR)	74.8	88.8	0.79	286.3
	ML Baseline (One-Hot OD + Quantile GBR)	96.0	98.3	0.74	279.5
	Baseline A (Context Median + Fallback)	118.9	142.0	–	–
	Baseline B (Hierarchical Backoff Median)	99.6	101.1	–	–
	Baseline C (Shortest Path + Fallback)	156.9	192.2	–	–
Hospital C	Proposed (Embeddings + Quantile GBR)	96.7	97.2	0.85	275.4
	ML Baseline (One-Hot OD + Quantile GBR)	109.3	111.4	0.96	294.0
	Baseline A (Context Median + Fallback)	166.6	170.8	–	–
	Baseline B (Hierarchical Backoff Median)	106.7	117.9	–	–
	Baseline C (Shortest Path + Fallback)	247.8	308.8	–	–

Layer II examines how travel time inputs propagate to system-level behavior in a trace-driven discrete-event simulation. All scenarios are simulated using identical transport demand, fleet size, and FIFO dispatching logic. No scheduling, routing, or capacity optimization is applied. Table 5 reports key performance indicators derived from historical observations (*Real*) and corresponding simulation outputs (*Sim*) for three hospitals. Real data is used only as a reference to assess the plausibility of simulated system dynamics.

Simulated porter utilization remains close to historical estimates in all hospitals. For Hospital A, utilization values are very similar (0.62 vs. 0.64), while for Hospitals B and C the simulated values are slightly lower than those observed historically (0.65 vs. 0.67 and 0.58 vs. 0.63, respectively). These differences are expected because the simulation models only explicitly recorded transport activities, whereas historical utilization may implicitly include unobserved periods such as informal coordination, interruptions, or equipment search.

The Backlog-related indicators are consistently lower in the simulated scenarios. Both average and peak backlog values decrease relative to historical observations, while task throughput remains largely comparable, with only minor reductions in completed tasks in some simulated scenarios. Under the simplified simulation assumptions, this results in a higher proportion of waiting time (e.g., 0.554 vs. 0.419 for Hospital C), reflecting shorter queue persistence rather than changes in demand or control logic.

Overall, the simulated indicators remain within a comparable range to historical observations. While the simulation abstracts from certain aspects of real-world operations, the resulting system dynamics are stable and operationally plausible, supporting the use of the evaluated travel time inputs for simulation-based analysis.

7. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper presented a data-driven framework for learning stochastic travel time inputs for internal hospital logistics and evaluating their operational impact through simulation. By combining graph-based representation learning with quantile regression, the proposed approach provides route-specific travel time estimates that generalize to unseen origin–destination relations. The results demonstrate consistent improvements in predictive accuracy and uncertainty calibration across multiple hospitals, compared to heuristic and tabular baselines.

TABLE 5. Layer-II performance indicators from historical data (Real) and simulation (Sim) for three hospitals.

Hospital	Source	Jobs	Porters	Utilization	Avg. Backlog	Peak Backlog	Completed Tasks	Empty Share	Loaded Share	Wait Share
Hospital A	Real	441	18	0.62	17	29	441	0.341	0.308	0.334
	Sim	441	18	0.64	9	14	441	0.294	0.301	0.405
Hospital B	Real	512	21	0.67	11	32	512	0.219	0.348	0.383
	Sim	512	21	0.65	8	13	504	0.193	0.361	0.446
Hospital C	Real	251	10	0.63	7	15	251	0.341	0.232	0.419
	Sim	251	10	0.58	3	4	249	0.221	0.225	0.554

Beyond prediction accuracy, the simulation-based evaluation showed that improved travel time inputs lead to stable and operationally plausible system dynamics under fixed dispatching logic and resource assumptions. While the simulation abstracts from certain unobserved real-world activities, key workload patterns and relative time shares remain consistent with historical observations, highlighting the importance of accurate input modeling for simulation-based hospital logistics analysis.

As future work, this travel time modeling component will be integrated into a larger multi-site simulation framework, enabling more comprehensive system studies. In this setting, arrival processes, human reaction times, and operational delays will be modeled explicitly rather than replayed from logs, allowing joint analysis of demand generation, execution dynamics, and resource interactions. This integration will support scenario-based evaluation of staffing levels, operational policies, and demand fluctuations, while preserving the data-driven calibration of travel time uncertainty developed in this work.

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